

**METHODOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF LESSONS AS A MEANS OF
IMPROVING THE TEACHER'S PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY**

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"Teaching is an art. In order to master this art, it is necessary to learn the ways of using several methods, in other words, to know the methodology of teaching." Professor Mirza Ismoilovich Makhmutov divides the development of methodological theory into three stages, notes four types of methods / educational method, teaching method, educational method, method of certain subjects and explains each method in detail. He writes: "The main content of the method is the idea of activity in it. An important feature of the method is that it always belongs to a person in action, because there can be no activity without a subject and a method associated with a specific action of the subject.

1. According to the organizational forms of teacher and student activities during the lesson:

- a) story method / in the form of the teacher's explanation;
- b) interview method.

2. On the basis of sources related to the facilitation of students' learning:

- a) radio broadcasting;
- b) working with a textbook;
- v) use of instructional tools /observing objects, the environment around the student, showing various models/;
- g) use of tape recorders and tape recorders.

When analyzing the educational system methodologically, the following are especially important:

- a) the purpose of education;

- b) content of education;
- c) forms of educational organization;
- g) educational resources;
- d) teacher's attention to educational methods.

The task of education is to gradually master the scientific method. When choosing a method, the main issue is to be able to identify an advanced method and master it, because the method in the content of education is the heart of understanding life. Some facts may be out of date, the method does not get old, it develops based on experiences.

It is known that the method used in each lesson should not only make it possible for the student to learn this or that concept, but should also be the only source of conscious mastering of these concepts. In the lesson, students' observations, experiences and personal conclusions are important. Because school programs are more than students. it requires independent work, and the teacher is mainly required to teach knowledge in class. Each of the teacher's lessons provides students with a conscious mastery of the topic, moving from live observation to abstract thinking and from practice. Only then will the student consciously recognize that every word said by the teacher is absolute. The imparting of concepts and knowledge on the basis of experience depends to a large extent on the existing conditions.

Laboratories and science rooms in schools are equipped with modern tools and equipment. The fact that eight-year and elementary schools are attached to secondary schools makes it possible to make perfect use of the existing educational materials in secondary schools. Therefore, in the methodical analysis of lessons, it is time to pay more attention to the available opportunities in the school.

The student's answer to the teacher's question is analyzed in depth. In some cases, some school leaders and teachers do not pay enough attention to the scientific basis of education. While there are laboratories, science facilities and

other facilities, the classes are conducted with dry lectures. Some teachers limit themselves to verbal explanations in lessons, without giving knowledge based on experience or proof, as a result of which students have difficulties in mastering the material. Some rules and definitions are silently written on cardboard and brought to class as exhibits. Such visual aids are useful for memorizing the rule, but they do not help to fully form in the mind of the student that the concepts and knowledge are real facts.

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